

The Nueva Escuela Mexicana reform in Mexico: Promises and tensions in revaluing the people's Mexico

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ABSTRACT

The *Nueva Escuela Mexicana* (NEM)—an education reform implemented in Mexico since 2023—represents a departure from previous neoliberal education reforms, emphasizing inclusion and diversity cultivated through active and project-based learning. As one of the first large-scale qualitative studies on the NEM, this study aimed to situate the reform within the experiences and challenges faced by educational stakeholders in Mexico, and to consider whether and how the reform may or will have contributed to addressing them. We carried out a total of 79 semi-structured individual and group interviews with various educational stakeholders in the three states of Nuevo León, Hidalgo, and Chiapas. The NEM was seemingly accepted by many participants because it helped “rescue” Mexican traditions and cultures, by contextualizing teaching and learning in their localities, and through the increased autonomy granted to teachers. However, several participants expressed their confusion about the potentially excessive flexibility in the NEM’s curriculum and pedagogy. The NEM also seemed to accompany a risk of “reverse discrimination,” as some people may not always have related so closely to the emphasis on Indigenous Languages and cultures. The article concludes with policy recommendations for the NEM, as well as for reforms implemented in similar contexts.

1. Introduction

In September 2023, the Secretary of Public Education (*Secretaría de Educación Pública*: SEP), which oversees and regulates the education system in Mexico, announced a new education reform called the *Nueva Escuela Mexicana* (NEM) to be implemented across all states and across all educational levels from basic to some higher education institutions. This reform represents a radical change in Mexican education: in contrast to the three decades of prior education reforms imbued with neoliberal principals (Ornelas, 2000, 2004), the NEM espouses humanistic and community-based approaches to integrate the genuine participation of teachers, learners, and communities in teaching and learning processes. The NEM recognizes the cultural and linguistic diversity in Mexico, promotes inclusive and intercultural education to respond to it, and aims to nurture students’ ethical and democratic values (*Secretaría de Educación Pública*, 2019, 2025).

This article presents selected findings from a larger research project exploring valued educational outcomes and pedagogies in Mexico in comparison with globally promoted learner-centered pedagogy (Bremner et al., 2024) and with historically nurtured pedagogies. In this article, we focus on the views and experiences of various educational stakeholders regarding the NEM in relation to their valued curricular and pedagogical processes. Given that the research took place in the very early stage of the implementation of the NEM, this article aims to provide immediate responses to the NEM and its on-the-ground realities from local perspectives. This will potentially contribute to improving the reform in its current implementation phase, considering that the NEM reform continues to be a matter of national interest and an ongoing process (*Presidencia de la Republica*, 2025). Our research can also pave the way for educational policy analysis and implication in other similar contexts.

In the following sections, we first introduce the context of education

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reforms in Mexico and explain in more detail what the NEM reform is. We then present the methodological and analytical approaches we took to address two research questions. This leads to our analysis and interpretation of the data in the following section. We begin by examining the participants' perspectives of the educational context in which the NEM was developed and implemented. The NEM was perceived to address some of the challenges that various educational stakeholders faced, for which some of the participants welcomed and embraced the newly arrived education reform. The NEM nevertheless brought unforeseen limitations; in this article we highlight struggles caused by the potentially excessive autonomy gained by teachers and an indication of "reverse discrimination" (Cardozo, 2012) observed in one of the studied states. We conclude the article with the policy implications as a possible way forward for the NEM, as well as for other educational reforms formulated and implemented in similar contexts.

2. Context and literature

2.1. Educational reforms in Mexico leading to the Nueva Escuela Mexicana

Mexico's education reforms have evolved in parallel with the political shifts the country has observed over the past several decades. The Institutional Revolutionary Party (*Partido Revolucionario Institucional*) dominated Mexican politics for most of the 20th century and maintained a centralized approach to education, emphasizing national unity and state control (Lozano, 2020). The subsequent two governments under Miguel de la Madrid and Carlos Salinas de Gortari shifted this orientation, following the global rise of neoliberal policies in the 1980s and 1990s; education reforms during this era focused on decentralization, privatization, and the promotion of competition and efficiency within the educational system (Ornelas, 2000, 2004).

This trend continued when the surrounding Latin American countries ushered in the so-called "turn to the Left" movement in the late 1990s and early 2000s. When countries like Venezuela, Bolivia, and Ecuador under their left-leaning governments rejected the neoliberal educational agenda in favor of public education, Indigenous rights, and anti-imperialist discourse (Escobar, 2010), Mexico remained under the control of the Institutional Revolutionary Party and the conservative National Action Party (*Partido Acción Nacional*). This led to the country's initial resistance to the broader "turn to the Left" movement; Mexican education reforms continued to reflect neoliberal principles, as exemplified by the 2013 education reform focusing on teacher evaluations and accountability based on their performance and productivity (Lozano, 2020). Ramírez Plascencia (2018) observed that this reform was heavily criticized as being a way to control teachers' labor conditions by centralizing authority and diminishing the role of unions in the education system.

The election of Andrés Manuel López Obrador in 2018 from one of the major left-wing political parties in Mexico marked a significant political shift toward the left in Mexico. A series of reforms under his administration across various sectors reflected a departure from previous neoliberal policies (Ruíz Galindo, 2024). In the education sector, the government abolished the controversial teacher evaluation system imposed under the previous government and effected a renewed focus on expanding educational opportunities for marginalized groups, including Indigenous communities and those in rural areas (Sandoval, 2023).

The NEM came out of this context under the rise of the new government toward the Left in Mexico. Marking a significant change to the previous reforms which had espoused neoliberal principles and priorities in education, the NEM reflects a vision of educational equity, inclusivity, and justice, especially for marginalized populations (Secretaría de Educación Pública, 2019, 2025). It claims to be innovative and disruptive and aims to radically transform the existing Mexican education system. This is to be achieved, according to Ventura Álvarez

(2023), through students' community participation, collaboration, multiculturalism, inclusion, and critical interculturality. In August 2023, just before the implementation of the NEM began, the then Secretary of Public Education, Leticia Ramírez Anaya, presented the ethos of the NEM at a press conference, stressing community as the core of teaching and learning processes, the reevaluation of teachers in their daily practice and professional autonomy, and the articulation of interdisciplinary work and project development (Ramírez Anaya, 2023).

2.2. Context and process of the NEM's development

While official NEM documents put forward the policy rhetoric introduced above, policy promises have tended not to translate into practices on the ground, given that policy actors often adapt, refine, and metamorphose the original, official policies when practicing them in their localities (Maguire et al., 2015; Skerritt et al., 2023; Fredriksen, 2023). At other times, unexpected policy outcomes divergent from the original objectives can emerge at the local policy level (Fulge et al., 2016; Rinne, 2020). Tekleselassie and DeCuir (2023) thus illustrated the key role played by local policy actors in resolving local educational problems, while George and Lewis (2011) argued for locally led educational policy development for the policies to take root in schools.

The NEM in Mexico claims to have been developed by incorporating the views, needs, and desires of civil society and teachers. To respond to the need to improve intergenerational social mobility and to address the inequalities reproduced in the educational system, López Obrador's government carried out a series of consultations with civil society in 2018 (Tiburcio and Jiménez, 2020). According to Jarquín (2023), the original ideas of the NEM gradually emerged from these consultations, as well as from monthly academic meetings called *Consejo Técnicos*, where teachers, along with various educational experts and civil organizations, submitted their opinions and ideas to the federal government. This bottom-up policy formulation process may suggest that the NEM endeavors to reflect the on-the-ground realities of teaching and learning at schools and to incorporate the opinions and suggestions made by local policy actors, the process recommended by Tekleselassie and DeCuir (2023) and George and Lewis (2011).

That said, the reform has been criticized for its lack of coherence and clarity in concepts, definitions, and theoretical underpinnings. Osuna-Lever et al. (2024) analyzed nine policy documents associated with the NEM and found the absence of key components required for a coherent educational policy (Fresan Orozco et al., 2017), including measurable goals, concrete strategies, and dedicated resources. Although the NEM documents present certain foundational ideas and knowledge forms, as well as the importance of technological integration and innovative pedagogies, they do not clearly define concepts introduced, describe its features, or provide a consistent reference point. This has led Osuna-Lever et al. (2024) to conclude the NEM as an ideological statement with conceptual and theoretical limitations, rather than a fully developed policy. According to some commentators (Ventura Álvarez, 2023), the vagueness attached to the NEM means it is an initiative without a clear direction, that may confuse educational stakeholders and is thus unlikely to translate into concrete implementation.

Given the above context of the NEM's development and its early stage of implementation, this study set out to situate the NEM within the experiences, challenges, and struggles faced by educational stakeholders in Mexico, as well as to consider whether and in what ways the reform may or will have contributed to addressing them. We asked two research questions:

1. How do policy actors in Mexico make sense of the NEM?
2. What, if anything, do their views and experiences of the NEM indicate about the reform's possible prospects and perplexities?

This study took place a few months after the NEM's implementation began in September 2023. While it is difficult to disentangle the mid-to

long-term effects of the NEM or its on-going practices within this study, our research can unpack some of the immediate responses and experiences of NEM implementation from the perspectives of people who practice the policy. Although academic research tends to take a long time to complete and be published (Björk and Solomon, 2013)—hence possibly informative and beneficial to the next phase of policy formulation and implementation—the findings from this study can also inform the NEM policy being implemented presently, potentially contributing to its improvement (if necessary and relevant) during the current implementation phase.

3. Methods

This study employed a qualitative methodological approach operationalized through semi-structured interviews. This allowed us to collect rich and detailed accounts of participants’ perspectives on valued pedagogies and their lived experiences of the NEM reform.

Although it was not appropriate to strive for statistical “representativeness” due to the qualitative nature of the study, we did aim to triangulate sources (Patton, 2015) by interviewing a range of different stakeholders from three diverse states: Nuevo León, Hidalgo and Chiapas. These states were chosen due to:

- *Geographical spread* (Nuevo León in the North close to the United States border, Hidalgo in the Centre close to the capital, Mexico City, and Chiapas in the South on the Guatemalan border).
- *Economic diversity* (Nuevo León was ranked 3rd out of 32 states in terms of GDP in the 2020 Census, with Hidalgo 19th and Chiapas 21st; INEGI, 2020).
- *Number of indigenous speakers* (The percentage of inhabitants speaking an indigenous language was 28.2 % in Chiapas, 12.3 % in Hidalgo, and 1.4 % in Nuevo León; INEGI, 2020).
- *Resource constraints*. Time and budget restricted us to three states.
- *Safety*. We were not able to travel to any areas of Mexico that the researchers’ governments had advised against all but essential travel at the time of the fieldwork.

Through the contacts of Bremner, we identified gatekeepers in each state and sent an introductory letter electronically stating who we are, the purpose and nature of the research. We asked the gatekeepers to identify four schools in their respective states. In order for a wider range of views to emerge, we ensured that there was at least one school designated as “urban” and one school designated as “rural” in each state.

Ethical approval was granted by the Hiroshima University’s Research Ethics Committee on May 12, 2023 (HR-ES-000961). Before entering the schools, the relevant educational authorities provided permission for data collection. Informed and voluntary consent was obtained from all participants, including learners whose parents gave consent through head teachers. Strict confidentiality and anonymity protocols were maintained throughout the project.

Data collection took place between October 2023 and January 2024. We visited 12 Mexican public primary schools and conducted a total of 79 individual and group interviews with 169 participants (Table 1). We individually interviewed 23 teachers, 12 head teachers, 1 deputy head teacher, 3 local teacher trainers, 4 local supervisors (who oversaw several schools in their respective regions), and 1 regional supervisor in Hidalgo, who was responsible for several school supervisors. We also conducted 24 group interviews with pupils, as well as 11 group interviews with parents (Table 2). We requested to interview teachers representing a diversity of experience levels and genders. Typically, this involved selecting one male and one female teacher (one with fewer than 10 years’ teaching experience and the other with more than 10 years’ experience). For the group interviews with pupils, we focused on students in 4th grade (ages 9–10), 5th grade (ages 10–11), and 6th grade (ages 11–12), as we believed that younger children might have found it more difficult to clearly express their perspectives on valued teaching

Table 1
Participants’ background.

State	Urban/ Rural	School pseudonyms	Participants	# of participants				
Nuevo Leon	Urban	Ignacio Allende	Head teacher	1				
			Teachers	2				
			Parents	2 (1 group)				
			Pupils	12 (2 groups)				
			16 de septiembre	Supervisor	1			
			Teacher trainer	1				
		Emiliano Zapata	Head teacher	1				
			Teachers	2				
			Parents	2 (1 group)				
			Pupils	8 (2 groups)				
			Rodolfo Neri	Supervisor	1			
			Vela	Head teacher	1			
		Hidalgo	Urban	Venustiano Carranza	Teachers	2		
					Parents	2 (1 group)		
					Pupils	8 (2 groups)		
					Semi- rural	Álvaro Obregón	Head teacher	1
							Teachers	2
							Parents	2 (1 group)
Pupils	8 (2 groups)							
Rural	Mario Molina		Head teacher	1				
			Teachers	2				
			Parents	2 (1 group)				
			Pupils	8 (2 groups)				
			Regional Supervisor	Octavio Paz	Head teacher	1		
					Teachers	2		
Parents	2 (1 group)							
Pupils	8 (2 groups)							
Chiapas	Urban				Diego Rivera	Supervisor	1	
						Head teacher	1	
			Teachers	1				
		Parents	2 (1 group)					
		Pupils	8 (2 groups)					
		Ex-supervisor of Benito Juárez García & Carlos Fuentes Macías Schools	1					
	Rural	Benito Juárez García	Head teacher	1				
			Teachers	2				
			Parents	2 (1 group)				
			Pupils	8 (2 groups)				
			Carlos Fuentes Macías	Porfirio Díaz	Head teacher	1		
					Teachers	2		
Parents	2 (1 group)							
Pupils	8 (2 groups)							
Teacher trainer	1							
Head teacher	1							
Teachers	2							
Pupils	8 (2 groups)							
Total number of participants				169				

Note: In Bremner et al. (2024), the total number of participants was quoted as 168 as the article counted 1 teacher who also acted as a parent as the same person, whereas in this article he has been presented as playing two separate roles.

and learning practices. Parents were invited by the Head Teacher on a voluntary basis, and were typically representatives of the parent-school committee.

We spent an average of two days at each school to complete all the interviews, but in some more geographically isolated schools we conducted all of the interviews in one day, arriving early and leaving after the children had returned home. During the individual and group interviews, we asked questions related to educational outcomes and

Table 2
Total number of participants by stakeholder categories.

Stakeholder categories	# of participants
Supervisors	5
Teacher trainers	3
Head teachers	12
Deputy head teacher	1
Teachers	23
Parents	25 (11 groups)
Pupils	100 (24 groups)
Total	169

pedagogies that the participants valued and desired to acquire through and beyond schooling, their understandings of pedagogy historically commonly used in Mexico, and their perceptions and experiences with the NEM in comparison with their valued and traditionally employed pedagogies.

Interviews were audio-recorded and later transcribed using the Notta transcription software. The transcriptions were carefully checked by a Spanish native speaker for accuracy. The transcripts were translated into English using DeepL translation software and subsequently checked by Bremner and Bórquez-Morales, who are proficient in both languages. Sakata and Bremner then used the qualitative data analysis software NVivo to facilitate their analysis of the data. Due to the highly rich, complex nature of the data, we decided to conduct our own separate inductive thematic analysis processes, following the steps typically recommended by Braun and Clarke (2021). This involved each researcher concurrently reading through each of the interview transcripts and creating codes as and when they emerged. These codes were refined through an interactive process over the course of several readings and re-readings. Once each of the researchers were satisfied with their individual coding, the two shared each other’s codes for detailed checking (analyst triangulation; Patton, 2015). Through a series of discussions, the researchers reconciled differing interpretations and agreed on a final set of themes which are elaborated upon in the next section. Our analysis in this article uses the data from adult participants in line with the themes focused on in this paper; another paper that we are currently writing delves into pupils’ perceptions and experiences with the NEM reform.

Regarding researcher positionality, Sakata is from Japan and approached the Mexican education system with relative neutrality, having relatively little prior knowledge of the culture and the Spanish language. Bremner is a UK national but had lived in Mexico for several years prior to this research project. Bórquez-Morales is a Mexican national with a deep understanding of the local educational system and thus provided context-specific expertise and support.

4. Findings

This section presents and analyzes the findings from the data. It first introduces the context of existing educational challenges experienced by the participants since before the NEM reform. It then moves on to introduce the aims and principles of the NEM that appeared to endeavor to tackle some of these challenges. We also present the participants’ views and immediate experience of the NEM. The last part of this section identifies potential limitations of the NEM which may be considered improving as it continues with its implementation.

4.1. Proud of Mexican culture, its diversity, and its roots

Some interviewees expressed their pride in the roots of Mexican culture before the Spanish arrived, as exemplified by a male parent at Ignacio Allende school (urban Nuevo León), who mentioned that “the culture that we have in Mexico is very, very rich. Very, very rich.” When we asked how the teachers at Camilo Pintado school (urban Chiapas) applied the NEM’s attention to traditions and community, the head

teacher started talking about the history of the country, stating that “Mexico was not born with the arrival of the Spanish, but has more than 5000 years of Olmec, Zapotec cultures, or here in Chiapas the Mayan culture.” This point was elaborated by another head teacher at Ignacio Allende school (urban Nuevo León) who asserted that “Mexico has very deep roots.” He continued to articulate the significance of pre-Hispanic culture and his respect for it:

The Olmeca and the Aztecs had their own culture. When you read about those aspects of the Mexican and Mayan cultures, we are talking about very important pre-Columbian cultures that transcended with certain things: the use of zero, zoology, botany. So, to ignore those aspects in this country would be very risky because Mexican culture is something that we all have in our blood.

Although these narratives imply the participants’ respect and pride for their own cultural roots, several interviewees indicated that these have been almost lost. After recognizing the value of culture—“Culture and traditions are two things that for me have to go hand in hand; if you don’t have culture, you lose tradition”—a parent at Benito Juárez García school (rural Chiapas) noted that “In reality, tradition here in Mexico is being lost.” The school supervisor in another rural region in Chiapas also lamented, “Mexican-ness is obviously being lost from our patriotic symbols; many of the fights and tributes have already been lost; identity is being lost.”

This notion of extinct cultural practices and values was particularly prevalent in the domains of Indigenous Languages. Several participants indicated that the older generations who were able to speak local languages were dying, whereas the younger generation, including the participants themselves, were no longer able to speak the languages. A female teacher at Octavio Paz school (rural Hidalgo) revealed, “the older adults who master the language are old and elderly, and they are disappearing, dying”; this belief led the teacher to maintain that “in the future, one day a language that used to be spoken will disappear.” Hñahñu, one of the languages spoken in this region, faced a similar situation according to a female parent at the same school:

The Hñahñu Language is a language that has been lost because many of the people who used to speak it have passed away. [...] If I could speak, I would teach my children and continue with the tradition. But our ancestors, our great-grandparents have passed away, and we no longer had the opportunity or the fortune to be taught.

Another reason why Indigenous Languages are vanishing is the negative social norm attached to them. Speaking of the Otomí Language, the head teacher at Octavio Paz school in rural Hidalgo mentioned the discriminatory practices against this particular language:

[M]any times, those neighbors, those colleagues who speak the (Otomí) Language, were ridiculed. When they spoke Spanish, they mispronounced some of the words, and they were mocked. So, they gave up on their language so as not to be criticized or bullied because of the way they spoke Spanish.

The loss of languages can lead to the loss of identity, as a parents in semi-rural Hidalgo implied:

[Our] mother tongue Nahuatl is hardly spoken anymore. If anyone speaks it, it is the older people. [...] (The town’s) name comes from Nahuatl, and few people know what it means. If the language is lost, then the knowledge that supports us as a people is also lost.

As such, several participants indicated their respect for and pride in their own culture; at the same time, they acknowledged and grieved that some aspects of the cultures and languages had been lost. Why, then, was Mexican culture considered to be lost? The next section investigates one of the potential reasons implied by the participants.

4.2. No Mexican educational grounding

The loss of Mexican culture observed by the participants might be partly attributable to the perceived lack of a unified educational grounding—be it the education system, structure, pedagogy or curriculum—that can pass on Mexican culture to the next generation. Many interviewees—notably head teachers—viewed that education in Mexico had been influenced by other countries and that something “Mexican” did not seem to exist in the educational sphere. Accounts like “Mexican teaching, Mexican learning does not exist. It does not exist” (a parent, rural Hidalgo) and “All (educational) models have been copied. Most of the models have been copied” (a male teacher, Octavio Paz school, rural Hidalgo) were commonly given. The head teacher at Octavio Paz school stressed the outside influence placed on Mexico: “We are influenced by other educational systems. At the moment, something Mexican doesn’t seem (to exist), because all the educational methods and models have come from other countries.” The head teacher at Porfirio Díaz school (rural Chiapas) referred to specific names of educationists from outside Mexico as examples of “borrowing”: “The books come from the ideology of Paulo Freire [...] pedagogues from a long time ago, for example Piaget and Vygotsky. They are the ones we follow.” The regional supervisor in Hidalgo considered this phenomenon as “a local and global construct” of educational ideas and practices which “reference[d] from other Spanish, English, Argentinean researchers, from various partners.”

Consequently, several interviewees underscored the absence of a unified pedagogical approach employed by teachers across Mexico. For example, a parent at Mario Molina school (semi-rural Hidalgo) stated that the fact that “there is a great diversity of languages and ethnic groups in Mexico” led to a situation that “everyone has their own way of teaching, and each ethnic group has their own way of teaching”. Some of the teacher participants also noted the context-dependent variation in ways of teaching: “I don’t think that there is one that all teachers were given, but everyone does it in their own way, with their own resources, with their own limitations.” (a female teacher at Mario Molina school, semi-rural Hidalgo).

Other teachers ascribed the lack of a coherent “Mexican” pedagogy to the country’s regional diversity. A male teacher at Benito Juárez García school (rural Chiapas) said:

[T]here is no one teaching (with) a Mexican essence. It would be difficult to find one because of the differences. From the North of the country to the center of the country and the South of the country, there is a lot of variety. I don’t consider that there is a single Mexican education.

Thus, there seem little shared understanding of educational grounding in Mexico to recover the traditions and languages that have allegedly become almost extinct. It would appear that, at least in terms of the policy discourse, the NEM arrived in this context to address these perceived challenges in Mexico.

4.3. NEM as the route to rescue Mexican culture

In detailing eight principles underpinning the NEM policy, the [Secretaría de Educación Pública, \(2019\)](#) lists “Fostering identity with Mexico” as its first principle—namely, that “The NEM fosters love for the homeland, appreciation of its culture, knowledge of its history and commitment to the values enshrined in its Political Constitution” (p. 4). It thus recognizes the need to nurture interculturality in children and “promote the recognition of cultural, ethnic, social, gender, environmental, and territorial diversity” ([Secretaría de Educación Pública, 2025, p. 6](#)).

These policy objectives seem to have trickled down to the local policy actors, and several participants considered the NEM to be “rescuing” the history and culture of Mexico. The head teacher at Octavio Paz school in rural Hidalgo welcomed the principles of the NEM, which “rescue, give value to what is local, to what belongs to the people,

to what is traditional, to what has been ignored,” leading him to believe that this reform as “good”. A male teacher at the same school, who expressed his regret at the loss of Mexican culture, also noted the aspect of “rescuing” traditions highlighted in the NEM:

There is a very strong emphasis on this, on the values of culture. That is emphasized a lot in the *Nueva Escuela Mexicana*. It is knowledge applied to your daily life [...] the relation to your daily life, your values, your principles. All these (things) that I would like to think (valuable) have been lost, and the *Nueva Escuela Mexicana* tries to rescue them.

This feature of the NEM, a female teacher at Emiliano Zapatas school (urban Nuevo León) thought, would enable “children (to) learn to value and rescue these cultures that are part of our traditions”. Rescuing values, traditions, and languages through the NEM could then restore the roots and identity of the Mexican people, several participants thought. A female teacher at Venustiano Carranza school (urban Hidalgo) said, “with this new educational model, we are looking to internalize, to discover, [...] and] it shows the students where their roots are, where they come from, where they are going.” This ethos can cultivate students’ sense of relationships between “the human being and the immediate environment” ([Secretaría de Educación Pública, 2022, p. 64](#)), which was elaborated by a supervisor:

It [the NEM] is giving priority to our roots as Mexicans, giving value to our mother tongue in certain areas of the country, giving value to our history, to our pre-Hispanic roots, showing us what the official history is, right? I understand that creating the whole concept of belonging goes toward the love for the homeland, for the student to discover his patriotic values, where he gives importance to where he comes from, and where our country is going. (A supervisor, rural Nuevo León)

How, then, does the NEM endeavor to realize this aspect of “rescuing” in everyday classes? The reform brought community lives and contextualization of the curriculum and pedagogy to the forefront of its agenda. The NEM pedagogical guidelines “promote various forms of participation that can take place between the school and the community,” with an expectation that the students “foster a deeper rootedness in local life” ([Secretaría de Educación Pública, 2019, p. 17](#)). [Tiburcio and Jiménez \(2020\)](#) observed the NEM’s commitment to the community and surrounding social and natural environments. According to [Monroy Segundo et al. \(2024\)](#), furthermore, this is meant to be achieved by allowing the community to actively choose learning themes and processes.

Several participants seemed to acknowledge this emphasis on community involvement and contextualization within the NEM. A male teacher at Porfirio Díaz school (rural Chiapas) noted that “the origin of pedagogy today in Mexico is to start from what the community has,” the point the head teacher at Ignacio Allende school (urban Nuevo León) elaborated:

The *Nueva Escuela Mexicana* seeks to start from the context of the school, the context of the community, in order to make a learning environment that is going to give the child the reality of what he is, the learning that is meaningful for him, (that) will have a meaning in his history as a human being.

When asked about how this aspect of the NEM had been implemented in everyday teaching, a female teacher at Mario Molina school (semi-rural Hidalgo) responded that she “look[s] for the activities and the contents that you think are going to help your community, the children in your community, those people in your community to develop in life, that are useful for life.” A female parent living in a community of a rural region in Hidalgo, also brought an example of what her child had experienced since the reform started:

They [the students] have focused more on the customs and traditions here in the community. For example, recently the teachers did a project. Well, in my girl's group, they did a project about the community, and its customs and traditions. They focused on the patron saint festival here: what is done, how people dress during the *fiestas*, what typical dishes they eat here in the region. That project was made by the children and presented to parents.

These teaching and learning approaches apparently practiced under the NEM correspond to its pedagogical guidelines; by regarding teachers as “key actors” in achieving what the NEM promises, the guidelines envisage them to have an “impact on the local and community level, and are aware of the main issues and debates that concern their practice” (Secretaría de Educación Pública, 2019, p. 18). A parent from a semi-rural area of Hidalgo compared the teaching and learning approaches previously taken to those used under the NEM. The latter allowed students and communities to select the topics that interested and were relevant to them:

Before, it was very much like this: we are going to work on this page and the next one, the next one, the next one, the next one. In other words, it [the learning content] was imposed. Not now. Now that is no longer imposed. Now we can be working on this page. There is a topic we are interested in, but it is on such and such a page. Then we go to that page and see if it is a topic that interests us all as students, as parents or family, as a community.

This quotation exemplifies what Tiburcio and Jiménez (2020) identified as the flexible and open characteristics of the NEM to allow for the diversity and contextualization of the curriculum and pedagogy. In attempting to realize these features, the NEM necessarily granted flexibility and autonomy to the teachers, to which our discussion now turns.

4.4. Teacher autonomy

Scholars have defined teacher autonomy as teachers' capacity to make informed decisions on curricular and pedagogical aspects of teaching based on their needs, values, and circumstances (Koestner and Losier, 1996; Narayanan et al., 2024; Wermke and Høstfält, 2014). Teacher autonomy is central to the teaching profession, and various studies have demonstrated its positive relationships with job satisfaction (Skaalvik and Skaalvik, 2014), motivation and commitment (Cribb and Gewirtz, 2007), and teacher retention (Fernet et al., 2014). The NEM, in promoting the adaptation of curriculum and pedagogy within a given context, points to the control and autonomy teachers possess in implementing the policy: It expects “to enhance the authority and responsibility of the teacher in the accompaniment and in their practice” (Secretaría de Educación Pública, 2019, p. 17).

This policy pronouncement appeared to have reached the local schools, as the head teacher at Mario Molina school (semi-rural Hidalgo) stated that “this educational model of focusing on communities and autonomy and freedom, I think, can allow us to attend to diversity.” In rural Chiapas, another head teacher at Porfirio Díaz school echoed this statement: “We now have all the autonomy, the teacher now has all the autonomy that we have never had before, to be able to contextualize learning.”

A supervisor who used to oversee two rural schools in Chiapas connected these two dimensions of contextualization and teacher autonomy stressed in the NEM:

The *Nueva Escuela Mexicana* has an open curriculum in which teachers are given the freedom to work and design their activities based on the socio-cultural context in which they are working, considering the local community, the educational community, and the people in general.

The teachers' freedom to adapt their teaching would allow them “to prioritize what strengths there are in the locality,” the supervisor added.

Vangrieken et al. (2017) categorizes teacher autonomy into content and pedagogical autonomy, with the former covering lesson preparation, choice of topics and textbooks, and goal setting, and the latter encompassing teaching approaches, time use, and student management. Several interviewed teachers agreed that both these aspects of teacher autonomy were embedded in the NEM. A female teacher at Venustiano Carranza school (urban Hidalgo) thought that the NEM was “a great opportunity” because “it gives me the freedom to manage my time, to manage my content, to utilize my skills a little more and to reinforce them, with the very purpose of giving these children a better education.” The newfound freedom was also translated into both curriculum and pedagogy being adjusted to students' needs, as expressed by a female teacher at Mario Molina (semi-rural Hidalgo) that “we as teachers have the freedom to choose the topics according to the problems that the students have.” Another female teacher at Rodolfo Neri Vela school (rural Nuevo León) also made a similar point:

[T]he teacher will take that content or those activities that favor the student. And if we see that they still haven't mastered them, then we can go back. We can follow them until we see that the children have mastered those skills or that knowledge.

Teacher autonomy, by virtue of freedom granted, also gave a space for some teachers to try out their teaching practices, allowing a female teacher at Benito Juárez García (rural Chiapas) who “like[s] to experiment, innovate and see if they work for me”. She said that “trial and error must bring me something. If it doesn't work for me, I can learn from the error so that the next year I can perfect it.” Her colleague at the same school similarly “built from scratch [...] a subject, my project, what purposes my project can have, what has to do with the student profile.” Such increased teacher autonomy allowed by the NEM made another teacher at Porfirio Díaz school (rural Chiapas) endorse it as the “most important thing” in the NEM reform.

While many participants embraced the autonomy they experienced through the NEM, a total absence of guidelines or regulations may still trigger confusion among teachers (Erss, 2018), and some interviewees—notably headteachers and teachers who observe and practice everyday teaching—expressed concerns about the perhaps excessive freedom teachers gained through the NEM (see details in Bremner et al., 2024). Consulting with class teachers at Venustiano Carranza school (urban Hidalgo) on a day-to-day basis, the supervisor reported the lack of confidence in teachers under her supervision:

My colleagues [teachers] are finding it difficult to plan their teaching, because there is no longer a specific way as before. (Teachers say) “Now I am going to shape it as I understand it,” and that is where they come into conflict as they ask me how they start. “I feel that my children are not learning,” “I feel that I am not organized as before”—so they are having a hard time.

Likewise, the head teacher at Porfirio Díaz school (rural Chiapas) expressed that it was a “barrier” that “the *Nueva Escuela Mexicana* gives us an autonomy that the teacher is not used to”; his fellow teachers were rebellious against the reform and told him that they “just want to pass it [teaching contents] on to the students. I don't want to complicate it. I want to be practical.”

Some of the teacher participants also seemed confused that they had too much room for adaptation and sometimes considered it as a lack of structure and guidance: “It [the NEM] leaves too much to the teacher to do everything. And there's not so much structure. There's not so much influence of the curriculum. Like there's no guidance. There's no direction” (A female teacher at Ignacio Allende school in urban Nuevo León). Her colleague at the same school made a similar point while typifying the situation with an example of driving:

There's so much freedom. A lot of times you lose the focus. They tell you, “Just go, you go where you think is convenient, you don't know

if you are right or wrong.” It is like when you learn to drive, they tell you that you have to get to your friend’s house, and you get there.

Consequently, “many teachers get lost in the objective they have—that they are looking for—and start to do activities with the students,” the teacher continued. A female teacher at Álvaro Obregón school (semi-rural Hidalgo) also expressed her concern that she was not able to take advantage of the freedom: “We are given a lot of autonomy for the teacher, but sometimes you can’t have that autonomy because you don’t really know how to design programs.” As claimed by Erss (2018) and Narayanan et al. (2024), a balance between control and autonomy, as well as a supportive environment with oversight by and feedback from other colleagues, will be necessary in order to allow teachers to confidently exercise autonomy under the NEM.

4.5. Regional difference in the views toward the NEM

In addition to the confusion these participants felt about the autonomous curriculum and pedagogy in the NEM, the views about its emphasis on traditional and Indigenous cultures also varied depending on the regions. Ranked 6th as the most linguistically diverse country around the world (Köster, 2016), Mexico presents huge cultural and linguistic diversity, which was acknowledged by some of the participants presented earlier in this article.

This cultural diversity seemed to translate into different degrees of enthusiasm toward the NEM depending on the region: the NEM’s emphasis on Indigenous community was more welcomed in the South but less so in the North. Nuevo León—the Northernmost state close to the United States border—does not contain many Indigenous communities (Durin, 2007), partly because “Nuevo León is a state where there is no mother tongue. There were no Indigenous settlements here in the state” (a parents, urban Nuevo León), and partly because the “area is very influenced by what happens in the United States” (a male teacher at Ignacio Allende school, urban Nuevo León). Supposedly, most students in Emiliano Zapata school (urban Nuevo León) “have no contact with Indigenous Peoples” (a female teacher), and this makes it “difficult” to implement the NEM at Ignacio Allende school (a female teacher).

Consequently, the majority of the stakeholders we interviewed in Nuevo León saw the focus on Indigenous Peoples and cultures as somewhat irrelevant to where they lived. A male teacher at 16 de septiembre school (urban Nuevo León) revealed that “they [the students] obviously don’t find it relevant for them to want to know more (about Indigenous Peoples)”; a female parent made a similar statement: “I feel that this (emphasis on Indigenous communities in the NEM) does not apply so much to Nuevo León. [...] They [the students] are not really learning anything because they are just learning single words. There is no deep learning about the Indigenous Peoples.” The head teacher at the same school also repeatedly spoke of the insignificance of the curricular focus on Indigenous Languages at her school:

[W]hat the children see is what the books or the teachers tell them, but they don’t interact with any children who speak (Indigenous) Languages. I mean, my point is, experience is not there for the children, not there for the teachers, not there for me. There isn’t.

These participants who did not identify themselves as having an Indigenous background seemed to distance themselves from the weight put on Indigenous values and traditions in the NEM. Such cases may represent what Cardozo (2012) called “reverse discrimination” in the context of Bolivia; the education reform espousing decolonizing and communitarian education in the country seemed to have left out the non-Indigenous population, who felt the reform being imposed was somewhat ethnocentric, a point also made by Bastidas Redin (2018). Although the experience of the Mexican participants in the current study did not necessarily present such heightened tensions between Indigenous and non-Indigenous populations as was the case in Bolivia, one of the interviewees, the head teacher at Emiliano Zapata school (urban

Nuevo León), spoke of the importance of acknowledging the non-Indigenous population in educational settings:

Mexico is not only about Indigenous cultures. There are many of us, and we have to give importance to all of them. [...] It’s not just the Indigenous classes. There are many classes or many groups that make up Mexico.

As such, the enthusiasm for and appreciation of the NEM’s emphasis on Indigenous values and cultures were especially prevalent in Hidalgo and Chiapas but less so in Nuevo León where Indigenous Peoples and cultures were less visible. Some people in Nuevo León did not see the emphasis on Indigenous values in the NEM as relevant to their immediate lives. If a focus on contextualization is equated with an emphasis on Indigenous Peoples, it could be argued that this is no longer genuinely contextualized. Although it would still be important and valuable for pupils to learn about Indigenous and diverse cultures in Mexico, there may be an argument for less time dedicated to such topics in states like Nuevo León where there are relatively few Indigenous inhabitants.

5. Discussion and conclusion

This study examined the perceptions and experiences of various educational stakeholders in Mexico regarding the recent education reform, the *Nueva Escuela Mexicana*. As one of the first qualitative studies on the NEM conducted at a relatively large scale, it brought together voices of a wide variety of educational stakeholders in Mexico on the reform. The findings from this study would be of value for the ongoing implementation of the NEM (Secretaría de Educación Pública, 2025; Presidencia de la Republica, 2025), as well as future education reforms in Mexico and beyond.

During the first year of its implementation, the NEM seemingly received acceptance and support from many adult participants in the study. The reform was seen as offering a solution to one of the important problems extant in society, specifically in relation to diverse Mexican cultures and traditions considered to be “lost.” According to the participants, the NEM helped “rescue” their cultural roots—notably Indigenous Languages—by focusing on the local, contextualizing teaching and learning in everyday life, and granting autonomy to teachers. Many participants embraced these aspects of the NEM to revalue Mexicanness and hand down the traditions through contextualized teaching and learning. It is notable that these perspectives seem to be shared across different categories of adult participants.

While the NEM appeared to earn much appreciation from some of the policy actors, others expressed their confusion due to what they perceived as too much flexibility in the NEM curriculum and pedagogy that they were abruptly provided. Both Erss (2018) and Narayanan et al. (2024) warned of the danger of the absence of a plan, structure, or teachers’ guides, which can lead to teachers feeling isolated and overwhelmed depending on the countries, cultures, and individual teachers’ years of experience. Several participants in this study correspondingly expressed their preference for having a more rigid structure as to what and how to teach. In some cases, this resulted in some teachers’ somewhat ignoring the granted autonomy and continuing the way they had taught before the NEM. It is therefore recommended that those implementing the NEM execute a certain degree of rigidity over its curriculum and pedagogy to balance between the autonomy of individual teachers and schools and broader control. It is also necessary to provide support and feedback for teachers on their teaching when providing certain freedom to choose and create curricular and pedagogical approaches on their own.

The NEM also seemed to be accompanied by a risk of reverse discrimination because of its emphasis on locality, contextualization, and Indigenous Languages and cultures, which people in some regions may not have felt was directly relevant to their daily lives. This potential danger of reverse discrimination may indicate a contradiction within the NEM; the centrality of teacher autonomy and contextualization within

the reform should theoretically allow teachers to de-emphasize Indigenous content in favor of locally relevant topics. However, the theoretical vagueness and the lack of conceptual clarity in the NEM (Osuna-Lever et al., 2024; Ventura Álvarez, 2023) may have confused the local policy actors when it comes to practicing teacher autonomy on the ground. In particular, the NEM does not seem to draw a clear line between “valuing locals and contextualization” and “valuing Indigenous cultures and traditions”. This might have caused people in some states—especially where there are fewer Indigenous Peoples—feel not as relatable to the NEM as others. The insufficient guidance and structure surrounding flexibility and contextualization (see above, also in Bremner et al., 2024) may have also played a part in such vague conceptualizations and boundaries surrounding the NEM.

It is too early to draw any conclusions regarding the potentially divided views toward that the NEM may possibly imply “reverse discrimination”, given that this research took place only a few months after implementation began. Nonetheless, similar educational reforms with Indigenous emphasis recently implemented by left-wing governments in other Latin American countries seem to have exhibited similar consequences. As introduced above, Cardozo (2012) and Bastidas Redin (2018) illustrated the Bolivian case where the tension among different cultural groups had heightened due to education policy focused on Indigenous Peoples and cultures. Venezuela adopted the Bolivian curriculum to transform Venezuelan identity based on liberty, cooperation, equality and Latin American solidarity, resulting in acute resistance by teachers who felt excluded and perceived the change as a threat to their social status (Abbott et al., 2017). These cases indicate that it would not be so simple to achieve the universal inclusiveness or hegemonic status through educational reforms imbued with emphasis on certain ethnic group(s) or certain cultural aspects. Hence, the NEM would carry the risk of reverse discrimination if it does not recognize the “heterogenous space of struggle and contestation” (Cardozo, 2012, p. 768) extant among diverse cultural regions in Mexico.

There were certain limitations of this study which may be taken into account in future research. Although the research obtained a relatively large-scale qualitative data, its qualitative nature collected at 12 primary schools in three states in Mexico do not allow its findings to be generalized to the whole population or other regions in Mexico. Thus, caution needs to be taken when interpreting the data so as not to assume that similar phenomena may necessarily be observed in other regions. Additionally, this research—conducted at an early stage of the NEM implementation—provided us an opportunity to explore the stakeholders’ immediate responses to and experiences with the reform on one hand; on the other, this may present a limitation that the views talked about in this article may have changed dramatically as the NEM implementation continues. As such, whether and how the NEM may have translated into concrete teaching practices or student outcomes were also difficult to untangle in this research. Future studies might seek to examine the mid- and longer-term consequences of the NEM reform. Exploring the NEM in other regions of Mexico would also contribute to incorporating broader views toward the reform, possibly leading to further contextualization of the reform in the coming years.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Borquez-Morales Lilia Sulema: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Validation, Supervision, Resources, Data curation. **Sakata Nozomi:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Validation, Software, Resources, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Bremner Nicholas:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Resources, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation.

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